

Bayesian Calibration of Finite Element C-spar Models using Digital Image Correlation

Carl Scarth¹, Jean Bénézech¹, Geir Olafsson², Vincent K. Maes², Janice M. Dulieu-Barton²,
Richard Butler¹, Andrew T. Rhead¹

¹Centre for Integrated Materials, Processes and Structures, University of Bath, Bath, UK

²Bristol Composites Institute, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK

AI Empowering Composites

24th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM 24)

Baltimore, Maryland, USA, 4th-8th August 2025

Bayesian inference

- All predictions are subject to uncertainty:
 - Manufacturing uncertainty.
 - How accurate are models?
 - Are tests representative of reality? Noisy measurements?
 - Unknown quantities e.g. internal defects/features, damage.
- **Bayesian inference** helps us quantify and reduce this uncertainty by using new data to learn about uncertain quantities

Decreasing uncertainty

Bayesian model calibration

- Bayesian model calibration uses **model outputs** and **experimental data** to inform predictions.
- Can account for uncertainties in model inputs, model physics, and in the test data.
- Example case study using:
 - Stereo DIC from Compression tests on a C-spar.
 - ABAQUS model with material, boundary condition, and geometric uncertainty.
 - Main challenge is handling large quantities of data spanning both **time and space**.

Can we use the DIC to verify the accuracy of the model despite the uncertain inputs?

Longitudinal displacement from DIC at 200kN

Longitudinal displacement from ABAQUS at 200kN

Experimental data

- Stereo DIC captured using MatchID, from compression tests on a composite C-spar undertaken at the University of Bristol.
- 48 plies of IM7/8552, QI layup.
- +4mm eccentric loading relative to neutral axis.
- Separate datasets from two camera pairs, each focussed on one flange + the web.
- Limit analysis to longitudinal and out-of-plane displacement, maximum load 150 kN.

DIC showing a) Longitudinal and b) out-of-plane displacement at 150 kN

Experimental configuration showing rig design and camera pair focus

ABAQUS model and uncertainties

- Modelled with 4536 SC8R continuum shell elements (9354 nodes).
- Simply supported at reference nodes.
- Uncertainty in illustrated boundary conditions.
- Geometric uncertainty in **ply thickness** (t_{ply}) and **corner thinning** (t_{thin}).
- Uncertainty in E_{11} , E_{22} and G_{12} .

Calibration methodology

- Following Higdon et al.¹, method for calibrating models with vector-valued output:

$$\mathbf{y} = \boldsymbol{\eta}(\boldsymbol{\theta}^*) + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$$

DIC point cloud Abaqus model Error

$\boldsymbol{\theta}^*$ = uncertain inputs we want to learn about:

$$E_{11}, E_{22}, G_{12}, t_{ply}, x_{RP}, K_{fixture}, t_{thin}, K_{spring}$$

- An inverse problem:
 - \mathbf{y} is known, $\boldsymbol{\theta}^*$, hyperparameters for $\boldsymbol{\eta}$, and magnitude of error $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ are uncertain.
- Solve by:
 - 1) Specify **prior distributions** for uncertain parameters from coupon data, parametric studies & engineering judgement.
 - 2) Feed in **data**: combined dataset of DIC, plus 100 Latin Hypercube Samples of ABAQUS model output.
 - 3) Sample from the **posterior distribution** using Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (No-U-Turn Sampler, NUTS) in Stan².

¹D. Higdon et al, "Computer model calibration using high-dimensional output", *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 2008

²Stan modeling language users guide and reference manual, Version 2.26.1, <https://mc-stan.org>

Output decomposition

- Total of **299,328** model output values from each of the 100 training samples, and **1,227,163** DIC displacements.
- Decompose into first $p = 7$ principal components of model output using SVD:

$$\eta(\theta^*) \approx \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i(x, t) w_i(\theta^*)$$

- Basis vectors ϕ_i capture spatial & temporal dependency.
- Gaussian process emulators for coefficients w_i capture dependency on uncertain model inputs.

Out-of-plane displacement

Longitudinal displacement

First 4 principal components at 150kN

Prior distributions

What do I **believe** about the uncertain inputs before the test?
Not a measure of variability.

Prior parameters: mean and standard deviation for Gaussian and Half-normal, upper and lower bounds for uniform

	Distribution	Parameter 1	Parameter 2
E_{11} (GPa) ³	Gaussian	150.0	9.0
E_{22} (GPa) ⁴	Gaussian	8.96	0.538
G_{12} (GPa) ⁴	Gaussian	4.69	0.281
t_{ply} (mm)	Gaussian	0.125	0.00625
x_{RP} (mm)	Gaussian	46.0	0.667
$\log(K_{fixture})$	Uniform	5.9	12.0
$\log(K_{pin})$	Half-normal	4.0	2.5
t_{thin} (mm)	Half-normal	0.0	0.51

Initial mode force-displacement gradient at reference node vs $\log(K_{fixture})$ and $\log(K_{rig})$, overlaid with prior distributions

³ HexTow® IM7 Carbon Fibre, Product Data Sheet, HEXCEL

⁴ E. Clarkson. "Hexcel 8552 IM7 unidirectional prepreg 190 gsm & 35% qualification statistical analysis report." NCAMP, 2019.

Results: Posterior distributions

Prior & posterior heatmaps

- Differences between blue and red show reductions in uncertainty
- Strong correlations indicate inputs have complementary or antagonistic effects

Posterior Predictions

- Run posterior samples back through model to get posterior prediction given “true” input values

Prior & posterior residuals

Prior and posterior residuals at 150 kN. Residuals are shown separately for different camera pairs

- We can subtract DIC from the model to visualise residuals highlighting highest areas of discrepancy.
- “Prior” residuals taken relative to model output using deterministic input values.
- Posterior residuals taken relative to posterior predictive mean.

Force-Displacement Trends

Prior and posterior force-displacement trends at fixed point X on spar surface

- Significant reduction in prediction uncertainty. Discrepancies attributed to observation error.
- Stiffer material response due to increased E_{11} better fits both longitudinal and out-of-plane DIC.
- Higher error inferred for out-of-plane displacement

Conclusions and outlook

- Demonstrated a powerful statistical toolkit for comparing FE models against DIC, while accounting for uncertainty in model inputs and test data.
- Overcame challenge of calibrating full-field model output using high volumes of data.
- Useful for validating virtual tests.
- Uncertainty in boundary conditions very important.
- Shift in modulus also noteworthy. Using a homogeneous linear value across structure in may be overly simplistic.
- Future work will extend further into nonlinear regime and consider failure.
- Long term aim to decide most informative future experiments via Bayesian Design of Experiments.

Preliminary uncertainty quantification study using Hashin failure criteria

Preliminary Design of Experiments using displacement at fixed location on spar

The research presented was supported by the EPSRC Programme Grant
'Certification for Design – Reshaping the Testing Pyramid'
(CerTest, EP/S017038/1)

Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council

CERTIFICATION
FOR DESIGN:
RESHAPING THE
TESTING PYRAMID

AIRBUS

BAE SYSTEMS

Rolls-Royce

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council

Thank you for listening!

